

Question raised by requestor

Many horses are transported in small trailers for two horses. I am looking for material to bring to the attention of the competent authorities what to look for when approving such means of transport, what should be there, how the watering system should be distributed, how to reconcile the provisions for the transport of horses from 1/2005 with transports in small means of transport where the journey for commercial purposes may take more than 8 hours.

Answer

Introduction

Transporting horses over short distances and the use of small two-horse trailers are subject to strict regulations in the European Union, particularly under Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 on the protection of animals during transport. This regulation sets out detailed requirements to ensure animal welfare, for both short and long journeys.

References to regulation (EC) No 1/2005

Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 applies to the commercial transport of live animals by road, including journeys exceeding 8 hours. The key provisions to consider for horses are:

1. **General welfare principles (Article 3):** General conditions for transport, which states that animals must be transported in a way that prevents injury and unnecessary suffering. This applies equally to small trailers.
2. **Conditions for transport vehicles and transport practices (Annex I, Chapters II and III):** All the provisions described in Annex I, Chapter II and Chapter III, are compulsory also for two-horse trailers both on short and long journeys.
3. **Specific requirements for long journeys (Annex I, Chapter VI):** All of the provisions described in Annex I, Chapter VI, are compulsory for two-horse trailers on long journeys, with specific precautions to be adopted; **feed and water supply:** a trailer shall carry a sufficient quantity of appropriate feed for the feeding requirements of the animals during the journey concerned and water supply that makes it possible to give each animal access to water whenever it is necessary during the journey. In two-horse trailers the watering equipment could be a mobile water device, as a bucket, which should be functional, easy to clean, and designed so that horses can access water without difficulty; **ventilation system:** horses can be scared if you equip your vehicles with the classic fans positioned on the sides of the vehicles. It is better to equip the vehicles with extractor fans positioned on the roof along with natural apertures to provide a uniform airflow. If a forced ventilation system is used on long journeys the ventilation system must be capable of operating for at least 4 hours, independently of the vehicle engine.

Final remarks

Although it is technically possible to obtain authorisation for using two-horse trailers for long journeys, this presents logistical and welfare challenges, especially in terms of ventilation and comfort. The latter is particularly difficult for foals and young horses since, according to the regulation, during long journeys foals and young horses must be able to lie down. Therefore, it is crucial that the Competent Authorities carefully assess compliance with regulatory requirements set out by Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 on the protection of animals during transport before granting authorisation for long commercial journeys.

Conditions for authorisation

To be authorised for journeys over 8 hours, two-horse trailers must meet the following requirements:

1. **Certification:** The transport vehicle must be certified for long journeys by the Competent Authorities in the EU country where it is registered. This certification ensures that the trailer meets the technical provisions set out in Annex I, Chapter VI of Regulation (EC) No 1/2005.
2. **Ventilation system:** The trailer must have an adequate ventilation system to maintain optimal internal temperature for the horses, especially in hot or cold weather conditions.
3. **Sufficient space:** Even in small trailers, horses must have enough space to stand in their natural position, move their head and neck, and should not be subjected to excessive stress or confinement (see relevant table in Chapter VII).
4. **Watering and feeding:** It is mandatory to provide horses with water and, if necessary, food during the journey. Trailers must be equipped with a system that makes it possible for the attendant to provide water instantly whenever it is necessary during the journey, so that each animal has access to water (water tanks). The total capacity of the water tank for each means of transport shall be at least equal to 1.5 % of its maximum payload. Water tanks must be designed so that they can be drained and cleaned after each journey and must be fitted with a system allowing their water level to be checked.
5. **Dividers and stability:** To ensure the animals' safety during transport, trailers must have internal dividers that allow horses to maintain balance during travel, especially when turning or braking suddenly.
6. **Access and inspection:** The trailer must be designed to allow easy access to the horses for inspections or emergencies during the journey. It must be possible to monitor the animals' health safely.
7. **Journey plans:** For journeys over 8 hours, a detailed travel plan is required, specifying planned stops for rest and care of the animals. These breaks must allow horses to be hydrated, fed, and rested (see also Annex 1, Chapter V).
8. **Navigation system:** Means of transport by road must be equipped with the appropriate navigation system allowing for recording and providing information including information about the opening/closing of the loading flap.
9. **Temperature recording:** Means of transport by road must be fitted with a temperature monitoring system as well as with a means of recording such data.

If registered horses are involved (as defined in the regulations, where registered horses refer to registered equids under Directive 90/426/EEC), certain derogations apply. Specifically, for journeys exceeding 8 hours, these derogations include:

- **Annex I, Chapter 5, Section 1.1:** Non-compliance with the maximum transport time limit of 24 hours. No specific conditions are outlined in the regulation.
- **Annex I, Chapter 5, Section 1.1:** Failure to provide water every 8 hours. No specific conditions are outlined in the regulation.
- **Article 6, Point 9:** Failure to equip the vehicle with a satellite navigation system. No specific conditions are outlined in the regulation.
- **Article 5, Point 4; Article 8, Point 2:** Failure to maintain a travel log. No specific conditions are outlined in the regulation.

References

1. Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 of 22 December 2004 on the protection of animals during transport and related operations and amending Directives 64/432/EEC and 93/119/EC and Regulation (EC) No 1255/97

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